

EOSC - Why & How?

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Marie

EOSC - Why & How?

Andreas

Hello and welcome to today's episode of Stories of Data - the Open Science Talk. I am Andreas Villarreal.

Marie

And I am Marie Czuray. Today we want to dive into the magical and mystical world of the European Open Science Cloud (in short: EOSC).

Andreas

Our big questions are: What is EOSC? And what's in it for me? And what for you?

Marie

For me?

Andreas

Yes, for you and for all the listeners of this podcast. So people working for research institutions, funding agencies, ministries and local governments or for the private sector, of course.

Marie

So what's in it for everyone who is interested in Open Science.

Andreas

Even for those who are not interested in Open Science.

Marie

Sounds like we have a really huge audience out there.

Andreas

Well, we hope so...

Marie

In our last podcast episode you talked about the European Open Science Cloud, how EOSC is more than a single project...

Andreas

Yes, absolutely, it is more than the sum of its parts, and encompasses many different processes and perspectives. And that is because in order to work, scientists require a wide range of resources and support - something the European Union has long been working to provide. A lot of the work being done in science depends on the access to research data, and on the tools to work with it in its various forms. This is what EOSC as a whole, is trying to facilitate - across multiple tools, multiple projects, and multiple websites.

Marie

This sounds all very nice... but honestly, I do not really get it. So my colleagues and I, we send out an email to the EOSC VIPs.

Andreas

The EOSC VIPs?

Marie

Yes, they are all very important people of the European Open Science Cloud. So the EOSC Association Board of Directors and the Steering Board Representatives.

Andreas

And what did you ask those EOSC VIPs?

Marie

We wanted their input for this podcast, so we asked them three questions. And the first one, which we'll cover in this episode, was: „How do you introduce EOSC to someone who has never heard about it before - What is EOSC?“

Andreas

Did they reply?

Marie

Yes, we got very interesting answers from them! I have them here.

Andreas

Wow, I am impressed. We got some pretty in-depth answers. Like this one: „How do you introduce EOSC to someone who has never heard about it before: What is EOSC?“ Their answer: “EOSC is an ambitious project - promoted by the European Commission - to meet future challenges in data storage and analysis to support policies on open science and open innovation. It aims to federate existing resources from a range of research infrastructures. It provides appropriate tools for data access and analysis. It supports the whole research data life cycle, from discovery to storage, management, analysis and re-use across disciplinary and national borders.”

Marie

I think it is important to stress that the European Commission was first pushing it forward. I also like

this answer: “EOSC stands for a world wide web of FAIR Data and Services. EOSC is not a new infrastructure or software package; it is a process of making research data in Europe accessible to all researchers under the same terms of use and distribution. The initiative aims to push Europe towards a culture of open research data that is FAIR.

Andreas

FAIR like Fair Trade, like the label?

Marie

Well, another kind of FAIR. This is the acronym for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

Andreas

There we have it. Thanks. Sounds like making data FAIR is quite an effort for researchers.

Marie

Some say, only FAIR data is real research data...plus, researchers also benefit from FAIR data provided by other researchers.

Andreas

True. Let's read another quote: “What is EOSC?” Answer: EOSC has to be seen as an interface. It's a European federation of FAIR data, services and e-infrastructures to accelerate research and to allow new types of interdisciplinary studies.

Marie

I have here also a good summary: EOSC is an initiative to define procedures, guidelines and interfaces in order to openly share and reuse research data and set up services to coordinate this process.

Andreas

One has to keep in mind that EOSC is not an electronic infrastructure (e-infrastructure) although it requires resources from e-infrastructures to build this concept up.

Marie

I looked through the answers of our EOSC VIPs, most explain EOSC both as a service to researchers as well as a broader idea.

So on the one hand, EOSC is an operation or an interface to build a virtual environment for existing scientific data infrastructures. The aim is to make it easier to find, access and reuse research data, tools and services. On the other hand, EOSC is also an idea. It seeks to interlink and combine data sets across disciplines and borders and to enable new and unexpected discoveries. And this benefits not only science, but also society as a whole.

Andreas

When I look through all these answers there are many aspects, like sharing data, e-infrastructures, expertise, financial, political, EU member states...

Marie

Right, it is indeed a big thing: EOSC stands for a change of culture in science. EOSC will be our future work space concerning FAIR handling of data and code in Europe. This process - remember, it's not a project - is already going on - one way or another.

Andreas

EOSC is the chance to get involved here in this culture change, helping to shape this new paradigm.

Marie

So, I collected some words that the EOSC VIPs used to describe EOSC: an environment, a tool to enable Open Science, a single platform, a work space, a web of research data, "The Google for research" and a "one-stop shop".

Andreas

What is a "one-stop shop"?

Marie

A business where multiple services are offered; for example, customers can get all they need in just "one stop".

Andreas

Ok, thanks.

Marie

So to continue my description list: EOSC is an initiative, an interface, an ecosystem, an utopia.

Andreas

Calling it an utopia would be quite contra-productive to our aim to make EOSC seem tangible.

Marie

Well, one has to consider that EOSC is a kind of utopia in the good sense, a mission and vision. Here researchers can share knowledge, collaborate and build together innovations. Thanks to the development of tools and standards. It concerns all the European countries and all the scientific disciplines.

Andreas

It's more than a challenge to address all these needs and to take diversity into account. EOSC is an ecosystem made by strategic, political, scientific, technical people and organisations at the local, national regional and European level. That explains the difficulty! EOSC designs the future of research in about ten years and it needs some vision to be achieved.

Marie

What is the European Commission doing to assist researchers in such a transformation?

Andreas

Here again, EOSC is the Commission's answer. EOSC provides the solution to the changing scientific practices: EOSC is providing access to relevant, high quality datasets. It can also offer services that can help researchers to process or analyse such data. Then later in their research lifecycle, EOSC can help them promote and share the results of their research thereby helping their career prospects and satisfying what is progressively becoming an obligation from funding agencies.

Marie

True, but at the same time it is also a frequent and time consuming task for researchers in any discipline to search for data that can support their research.

Andreas

Yes - however, never before it has been easier than now! Over the past decades, some trends have changed the way of doing science: Scientific research increasingly involves very large datasets (e.g. genomics data, telescope observations). Also, open access research - data, publications, software - has become one of the most powerful instruments to share knowledge and put it at the disposal of other researchers that can use it for a different purpose.

So in conclusion, as per what we wanted to know about EOSC in the beginning: "What's in it for you and me?"

Marie

So all the benefits for society as a whole are not enough?

Andreas

Well, you know, sure...but I mean on a daily basis, what's in it for me?

Marie

To sum up the answers of our EOSC VIPs, the most used examples are "easier access to data" and "data sharing". I would say for researchers the biggest benefit of EOSC is efficiency. They have easier access to data, publications, tools and services. Researchers can also take advantage of reusable data, and get higher visibility for their own research. In addition, quite often it is expected from them that they get involved in Research Data Management in order to meet the obligations of funding.

Andreas

Regarding fast access to high quality of data processing and analysing services, I would like to point out the EOSC Portal, which offers services for research from top European providers. If you are interested, check out eosc-portal.eu.

Marie

Thanks, Andreas, that's also a nice bridge to promote our next episode. Next time in Stories of Data, our topic is: EOSC - How to use it? We will present practical examples in order to support researchers to implement Open Science. And it will be again an episode with contributions of the EOSC Association Board of Directors and the Steering Board Representatives, whom we want to thank at this point for their time and interest to contribute to this podcast.

Andreas

And thanks also to all our listeners for their time and interest!

Marie

Yes, thank you very much. I'm really looking forward to our next podcast episode, and I hope you listeners will join us for that!

Andreas

Until then, take care, stay safe, and stay curious!

Marie

Bye!